

Investigation Of The Phosphorous Behavior In Basic Oxygen Furnace Slag by Carbothermal Reduction For Enhanced Slag Valorization

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1. INTRODUCTION

Iron- and steelmaking generate high amounts of by-products such as slag, dust, sludge, and gases, whereby slags make up 90% of the accumulated mass. In 2021, based on the blast furnace / basic oxygen furnace route, around 88 million tons of crude steel was produced in the European Union (EU27), representing 56,1% of the total crude steel production volume. Therefrom, around 400 kg slag / t crude steel occurs, whereof between 100 – 150 kg of slag can be attributed to the refining step in the converter [1, 2]. During oxygen blowing in the refining step, basic oxygen furnace slag (BOFS) originates by adding typical slag formers. Besides the uptake of unwanted elements for crude steel like phosphorus (P), also considerable amounts of valuable metals, including iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), and chromium (Cr), inevitably enter the slag mostly in their oxidic states. This results in a total content of valuable metal oxides of about 37 m.-%, expressed as Fe₂O₃, MnO, and Cr₂O₃ species in BOFS from a voestalpine steel mill (Austria) and about 2 m.-% of P₂O₅ [3, 4]. Thus, a high potential of precious constituents in BOFS can be identified, whereas a pyrometallurgical recycling process introduces a promising approach to make these recyclables available. Obtained fractions from the treatment are a metal fraction (MeF), consisting of Fe, Mn, and Cr, and a mineral fraction (MiF) of all non-reducible oxidic components. Furthermore, during the removal of oxygen from P-containing oxides, which is Ca₃(PO₄)₂ (C₃P) in the case of BOFS, highly reactive gaseous P (P₂) originates. As a result, contact between P₂ and a metal bath simultaneously leads to the formation of undesirable metal phosphides. High P-contents in the metal are unfavorable for valorization in the steel industry. By increasing the gasification rate of P and considering the high quantities of annual produced BOFS, a recovery of the bound P can promote the mitigation of the EU27 phosphate rock import dependence [5]. Therefore, the Chair of Thermal Processing Technology at the Montanuniversitaet Leoben (Austria) has developed a reactor concept that tackles the challenges of high-temperature treatment of P-rich waste streams [4, 6, 7]. One issue implies the effect of the valuable metal content of Fe, Mn, and Cr in BOFS on the gasification rate of P and, thus, on its tendency to form phosphides. For this reason, a deeper understanding of the P behavior as a function of varying amounts of Fe, Mn, and Cr is carried out by results from practical experiments with BOFS and synthetically produced slag systems, respectively.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a preliminary test series the general affinity between P and each individual valuable metal species in BOFS is investigated. Used materials are synthetically produced slags containing only one valuable metal oxide species. For that reason, chemicals in powder form (purity >97%) were mixed in a specific ratio, representing characteristic concentration ranges. As main slag oxides serve CaCO₃ as a CaO source, SiO₂, MgO, and Al₂O₃ were used. In addition, C₃P as P species was added, while valuable metal oxides, either Fe₃O₄, MnO₂, or Cr₂O₃ were applied, where each sample contains six oxidic species. In total, six samples were investigated, whereof three with Fe, Mn, and Cr contents of 4 m.-% and three with Fe, Mn, and Cr contents of 17 m.-%. All samples have a basicity B₂ of 1,4, expressed as the ratio of the m.-% between CaO and SiO₂. After mixing a total mass of 40 g, synthetic slag samples were produced via melting the mixtures in a resistance elevator furnace type ELHT 16/18 from Thermconcept

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at 1873 K with a holding time of 30 min and a heat rate of 300 K/h using a ceramic crucible (MgO). The solidified and cooled slags, extracted from the crucible, were crushed in a jaw crusher from Retsch model BB50 to a fixed grain size of 0,5 mm. The produced slag was analyzed for its elemental composition by inductively coupled plasma emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) to establish comparability with the calculated slag composition. Subsequently, the stoichiometrically required reductant amount of pulverized Carbolux[®] pellets with a surplus of 25% was calculated and added to the slag mixtures. In a heating microscope of E. Leitz Wetzlar, approximately 0,1 g in the form of a pressed cylinder consisting of the carbon-slag mixtures was tested for its melting behavior. Hence, in an electrically heated furnace chamber under an argon gas volume flow rate of 2 l/min, the cylinder was heated up to 1873 K, continuously illuminated frontally by a light source. Consequently, the change in the cross-sectional area of the cylinder was detected, which is an indicator of sintering-, softening-, or melting processes. Then, 15 g of the slag carbon mixture was treated carbothermally with the same heat rate, maximum temperature, and crucible for the melting step but under an inert atmosphere using argon with 4 l/min in a resistance furnace of Nabertherm. Finally, the formed product phases were manually separated from the crucible into a MiF and a MeF, which were analyzed by ICP-OES. In addition, scanning electron microscopy - energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) was used to identify formed phases and their composition.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first step, a theoretical consideration of the thermodynamic spontaneity of relevant phosphide formation reactions was presented using a plot of Gibb's energy as a function of temperature referring to reactions from literature, summarized in **Figure 1** [8]. The left red dotted line in both diagrams marks 1473 K, the minimum reduction temperature of C_3P from a thermodynamic point of view, which is increased without the attendance of SiO_2 to 1750 K, resulting in the gasification of P. The right dotted line in both diagrams represents the maximum temperature of the reduction experiment. In general, it can be seen that a high affinity can be found for all investigated valuable metals.

Figure 1: Gibb's energy vs. temperature for characteristic phosphide formation reactions, data from [8]

Besides insufficient melting properties, resulting in sintering processes for all samples with a low metal content of 4 m.-%, these samples could not be reduced. Thus, a separation into a MeF and MiF was not possible. One explanation is an improper melting point due to the choice of the slag systems composition. In addition, the contact probability between reductant and valuable metal oxide was possibly too low, which can be attributed to the minor amounts of existing Fe, Mn, and Cr. However, melting and reducing all samples with high metal contents of 17 m.-% was successful. Despite the Fe-rich sample showing strong interaction with the ceramic crucible material, resulting in material loss through the crucible bottom, metal could be recovered. Both the metal phase of Fe- and Cr-samples were enriched with P, showing similar behavior. Within the green-colored MiF of the Cr sample, which still indicates a high amount of unreduced Cr_2O_3 , tiny metal droplets of metallic Cr via SEM-EDS were detected. For the Mn-rich sample, in turn, no metal phase was formed. Instead, a segregation process of the initial slag sample into a dark-colored Mn-enriched MiF and a light-colored Mn-depleted MiF occurred. SEM-EDS analyses show that P is only present in the Mn-rich MiF, whereby no P can be found in the light-colored one. Due to problems with the refractory lining of the elevator furnace, the reduction step was carried out under non-ideal reduction conditions in a different furnace type. The results of the analysis are given in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Analysis results – a): ICP-OES of the MeF and MiF of the Fe- (S4), Cr- (S5), and Mn-rich (S6) sample; b): mapping by SEM-EDS of a representative grain from the MiF of the Mn-rich sample S6

4. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Outcomes from this work reveal that besides Fe, Cr and Mn also show a strong affinity to P during the carbothermal reduction of synthetically produced slag systems. While the behavior of Fe is similar to that of Cr, whereby P dissolves during carbothermal treatment in the metallic fraction in the form of phosphide species, Mn has shown a deviating behavior. The analysis of the segregated MiF has confirmed that P could only be determined in the Mn-rich slag system, which underpins their affinity. However, poorer reduction rates and differing behavior during carbothermal slag reduction of Mn compared to Fe and Cr are already known [9]. At the moment, further experiments are being carried out, investigating a wider range of relevant slag compositions. These test series imply improvements regarding the experimental setup and detailed analysis of the gained fractions.

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